

Drugs and Society: A Sociological Study

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Abstract

The problem of drugs is one of the problems that is not limited to one society or another or one class or another, as the phenomenon of drugs is considered one of the most common phenomena, which has become a great danger to societies and threatens their stability through the increasing spread of this scourge and its rapid and continuous development, and it also targets Primarily a group of young people and adolescents across the various historical stages of human life. So that it has become one of the most important problems facing countries with their bodies and social institutions. Which resulted in negative behavior and criminal deviations among societies, and thus the authorities in all countries of the world established a set of mechanisms to prevent and put an end in order to combat this social scourge that has hindered the pace of development and progress of societies. The importance of this topic lies in the fact that it is one of the important topics in the life of the individual and society, so that it has become a subject of study for many historians, researchers and scientists who have given it great importance in all economic and cultural aspects in the world of crime, as this topic has received a great deal of attention not only because of its seriousness, but For other reasons, which are the difference in researchers' views regarding drugs themselves. This is with the aim of knowing the reasons and motives that lead young people to resort to drug abuse, and through this measure it is possible to know the extent of the impact of addiction on the group of adolescents and their use of warnings, which relate primarily to socialization institutions and which appear clearly throughout the family system.

Linguistic concept of drugs:

The origin of the word pillows in the Arabic language is caution, and caution means concealment, and it is said to be a warning slave girl if she is bound by numbness, that is, she covers herself with it and no one sees her. Hence, the word drugs was used on the basis that it dulls the mind (Brahmiyya Nasira 2013, p. 16.)

In the French language, we find the term Drogue meaning a substance used for medical purposes alone or by mixing it, and it works to change the function of cells or organs (Himer Zoulikha, 2018, p. 4)

The origin of the word drugs in the Arabic language comes from the verb drugged, which means to cover up, and it is said that a slave girl is drugged if she is bound to be drugged, meaning she is hidden, and from here the word drugs was used on the basis that they are substances that cover the mind and make it absent (Sawsan Shaker 2008, p. 172)

Ibn Manzur mentioned that drugs are derived from numbness, that is, covering the slave girl in the area of the house, and the drug and numbness are extreme darkness, and the numbness is sloth, and numbness in the language is a spasm that affects the organ so that it cannot move, and therefore the drug, intoxicant, and wine are covering

Terminological concept of caveats:

It is every intoxicating, natural, or chemically prepared substance that removes the mind partially or completely, and consuming it leads to addiction, resulting in poisoning of the nervous system, harming the individual and society, and it is prohibited to circulate, cultivate, or manufacture it except for purposes determined by law and in a manner that does not conflict with Islamic law. (waqfi Hamid Abu Ali 2018, p. 121)

It is considered a chemical substance that causes drowsiness, sleep, or loss of consciousness, accompanied by pain relief, and the word anesthetic is a translation of the word "Narcoteque", which is derived from the Greek "Narcosis." It means numbing and making a drug, and it is defined as a raw material or preparation that contains stimulant or analgesic substances if used for health or industrial purposes that lead to A condition that returns and repeated use of it makes the individual addicted to it (Bouhara Hanaa, 2017, 283 pages)

Legal definition of drugs

Islam defines the drug as what covers the mind and what intoxicates the difference, so filling the palm of it is forbidden. (khaled Hamad Al-Muhannadi 2013, p. 23)

Drugs are called slanderous drugs, meaning those that make the mind and senses absent without causing that euphoria and pleasure, but if that is accompanied by euphoria, then it is intoxicating, and therefore drugs are compared to alcohol in their rulings because they participate in the reason for the ruling.

The rulings of Islam follow from preserving the human being and his dignity and preserving the public interest. The legal rulings work to preserve the mind and prohibit everything that destroys the mind, corrupts it, or causes any harm in the short or long term, whether to the individual's personality, religion, family, or society.

Just as Islamic law forbids sugar and alcohol of all kinds, it forbids everything that destroys or corrupts the mind, whether it is liquid, solid, or gaseous, for wine covers the mind. The Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, made clear the prohibition of what covers the mind definitively, and he did not differentiate between one type or another or whether it is food or drink, and accordingly Therefore, drugs of all kinds cover the mind, and therefore they fall under the ruling of intoxicants, and they are eaten, drunk, smelled, and injected, and all of that is forbidden

Sociological definition of drugs:

It is every natural, artificial, or chemical substance whose properties lead to the phenomenon of endurance, habituation, and addiction, and lead to a state of calm, sleep, relaxation, activity, attention, and hallucinations, and abstaining from it leads to the emergence of psychological and physical disease symptoms that are dangerous to the individual and society.

They are also known as those substances that lead the user and those who use them to delinquent behavior, and according to social specialists, they are also those substances that dull the mind, causing the user to engage in deviant behavior. (rajab Muhammad Abu Jannah 2000, p. 30)

It is everything that confuses the mind or numbs it and changes the thinking of the individual's personality, and there is a difference between habituation and addiction by getting used to a stage that leads to addiction, which is a state of longing to use the drug, a compulsive

desire among the habitual to go too far and get used to it, while addiction is dependence on the narcotic substance, relying on Psychologically and physically (Muhammad Jamal Matloub, 2012, p. 7)

Legal definition of drugs:

It is a group of substances that cause addiction and irritate the nervous system, and its circulation is prohibited for legal purposes and is only used by those licensed to do so

It is stated in Article 2 of the Algerian Law relating to the Prevention of Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances and the Suppression of Illicit Use and Trafficking in them: "The drug is any synthetic substance mentioned in Tables One and Two of the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs in 1961, as amended by the 1972 Protocol" (Ministry of Justice 2005, Algeria, p. 03)

Medical concept of drugs:

Drugs mean those natural, prepared substances that are capable of causing change in mental activity with a psychological and physiological effect, and they are two types of permissible drugs, which are generally medicines available in pharmacies for medical purposes and prohibited drugs, and they are either a natural plant such as hashish or Indian hemp, or prepared such as processed kif, and they are used for addiction with the intention of changing the activity of Natural mind. It is every substance, whether plant, chemical, or compound, that has certain properties that affect its user and make him involuntarily addicted to it, with the exception of taking it for the purposes of treatment for some diseases and according to medical supervision, and it constitutes harm to the user, whether psychological or health. Abdul Rahman Shaaban Attiyat believes that the drug is a natural or manufactured substance with biochemical properties characterized by its ability to affect the cerebral nervous system, which leads to physical, mental and psychological disorders among its users, and the drugs include opium and its derivatives of morphine, heroin and others, and these substances are subject to international control (Saad Drevel, 2011, p. 27)

International Convention on Narcotic Drugs definition:

International agreements unanimously defined drugs as natural and synthetic anesthetics subject to international control in 1961, which is known as the only agreement, and it is what was confirmed by the Psychiatric Substances Convention in 1971, Afri Naji (Rajab Muhammad Abu Jinnah, 2000, p. 29)

Drug-related terms

Addiction: means the repeated use of a psychological substance to the point that the user reveals extreme preoccupation with the user, and an inability or refusal to stop using it. He often shows withdrawal symptoms if he stops using it and his life becomes under the control of abuse to the point of excluding any other activity (Khaled Hamad Al-Muhannadi, 2013, p. 47)

Eagerness: A strong desire to obtain traces of a drug or an alcoholic drink, and eagerness has some obsessive characteristics, as it does not occur to the addict's mind and is often accompanied by bad feelings (Mustafa Suef, 1996, p. 18)

Dependence: A psychological state, sometimes organic, resulting from an interaction between a living organism and a psychological substance, this state is characterized by the issuance of responses or behaviors that always contain an element of the desire to use the

organism as a specific psychological substance on an ongoing or periodic basis, and the person also depends on one substance or More (Khaled Hamad Al-Muhannadi, 2013, p. 52)

Psychological dependence: A situation found in a feeling of satisfaction with a psychological motive, which requires continuous or periodic use of a psychological substance, and this psychological state is considered the strongest factor involved in chronic poisoning with psychological substances, and in some substances the condition is the only factor involved in the situation.

Organic dependence: an organic adaptive state that reveals itself with the emergence of severe organic disorders, in the event of a cessation of the presence of a certain psychological substance, and these disorders consist of a group of symptoms called withdrawal symptoms, and they can be eliminated by the person returning to taking the same psychological substance or another substance. It has a pharmacological effect, and organic dependence is considered a strong factor in supporting psychological dependence and its effect in continuing to use psychological substances (Mustafa Suef, 1996, p. 18)

Neuroadaptation: The sum of the neurological changes associated with both endurance and the appearance of withdrawal symptoms, in some cases these changes are annoying, as in the case of opioids, and it is possible for neuroadaptation to arise without noticing any cognitive or behavioral manifestations (Mustafa Suef, 1996, p. 22)

Endurance: an organic, physiological change, which tends to increase the dose of addiction with the aim of obtaining the same effect that was possible before, endurance can occur due to psychosocial factors, and endurance may be organic or behavioral, and organic endurance is a change in future cells and behavioral endurance A change in the effect of the substance used, while behavioral tolerance is a change accompanied by an increased response to the same dose of the substance used (Saeedi Atiqah, 2016 p. 144)

Withdrawal: A group of symptoms that differ in some of their vocabulary and in their severity that occur to the individual as a result of sudden cessation of taking a psychological substance, or reducing its dose, provided that the use of this substance may be repeated frequently, its symptoms are accompanied by signs of a physiological disorder, and the state of withdrawal is considered evidence of That there was a state of dependence (Mustafa Suef, 1996, p. 24)

Abuse: It represents the first stage of addiction, including experimental or exploratory abuse, which is a psychological abuse process in its experimental stage, and the user's attempt to explore his conditions with them until this results in either continuing to abuse it or stopping it, as well as intermittent abuse, and that is all that was. A social occasion that calls for endurance (Mustafa Suef, 1996, p. 25)

Types of drugs and their harms

Cannabis (how): It is made from the resinous substance of the buds, leaves, and flowers of a female tree of the cannabis plant, and place it in the form of a paste or mold. Cannabis contains the active ingredient THC, which is anesthetized in an amount equivalent to 5 to 10 times what banjo contains, and it cannot be obtained in Pure form, for purposes in scientific research only, because it is extracted in its pure form. In general, the percentage of the active substance in THC ranges between % 3 to 10% and is known to the public as (Zatla).

(Daoud Alajjiya, 2008, p. 10) Its harms and effects lie in the following:

- It affects some nerve conductors, causing depression and the inability to remember, concentrate, and pay attention, and taking it for many years leads to brain atrophy.
- Its owner suffers from symptoms of poisoning after its effects disappear after days or weeks of use.
- Suffering from auditory and visual hallucinations, as well as loss of awareness of what is around him. (Muhammad Munawar Al-Mutairi, b.T, p. 4)

Qat: It is a multi-branched evergreen plant with lemon-like leaves, its name is *Katha Yedus* Forsk (Himer Zulekha, 2018, p. 7). It is taken by storing it in the mouth and chewing it. Doctors believe that khat does not have any health benefits as some users imagine (Raqiq Najma, 2016-2017, p. 136.) Its harms lie in the following:

Its addiction leads to an increase in blood sugar, and its users are more susceptible to diabetes.

- Reduces the level of protein in the blood, which leads to circulatory disorders and high blood pressure.
- Inflammation of the stomach, lack of secretions, paralysis of the intestines and urethra, liver damage, weak structure, and wheezing with lack of activity (Muhammad Manawer Al-Mutairi, b.T, p. 08)

Opium: A dried milky liquid resulting from the fruits of the poppy plant, as it is a white milky sap that turns dark brown in color, has a bitter taste and has a pungent odor. (Samir Abdel Ghani, 2009, p. 51.)

Its effects and harms are as follows:

- It destroys brain cells and leads to some mental disorders.
- Its use leads to complete atrophy of the body's muscles in addition to poor memory.
- There is a decrease in blood circulation, which leads to sudden death.
- Kidney and liver damage, dry mouth, and high blood pressure. (Muhammad Munawar Al-Mutairi, b.T, p. 10)

Heroin: It is extracted from the poppy plant from the spike or fruit, and is used by subcutaneous injection, intravenous injection, oral swallowing when it is tablets, or by smell, if it is a powder, and it is considered one of the most dangerous types of drugs. (Iman Muhammad Al-Jabri, 2011, p. 20) Its harms are as follows:

- Insomnia and mental illnesses such as depression.
- Pneumonia and tuberculosis.
- Vein blockage as a result of repeated injections.
- Serious skin infections.
- Heart disease, kidney failure, and cirrhosis. (muhammad Manawer Al-Mutairi, b.T, p. 12.)

Cocaine: It is extracted from the coca plant, and is taken either by injection, smell, smoking, or by massaging the mucous membranes of the mouth. It is used for medical purposes

by dentists to relieve the mother for surgical operations, and it is also used by surgeons as a local anesthetic. (nasr al-Din Maruk, 2007, p. 45) Its dangers lie in the following.

- Its users suffer from blurry vision and dilated pupils
- Anxiety, stress, constriction of blood vessels, and nosebleeds.
- Rapid breathing, sweating, chest pain, heart disease, and kidney failure.
- Its injection leads to gangrene in the intestine due to decreased blood flow and the appearance of allergic diseases.
- Infection with AIDS.
- Loss of sense of smell, swallowing problems, and hoarseness (Muhammad Al-Jabri, 2011, p. 14)

Marijuana: Extracted from the cannabis plant, it was first used in cases of headaches and insomnia, but its use has ceased and it is no longer prescribed in medical tickets. It is considered one of the drugs that usually induces addiction and is commonly used in America, and it can only be obtained through illegal trade and Smuggling, and the US government has taken all steps to monitor cannabis cultivation. (khaled Hamad Al-Muhannadi, 2013, pp. 40,41) Its dangers lie in:

- Redness of the covering layer of the eyes.
- Imbalance.
- Rapid heartbeat and high blood pressure.
- Psychological disorder increased anxiety and stress.
- A feeling of fatigue and a desire to sleep, causing depression among those who use it (Muhammad Munawer Al-Mutairi, b.T, p. 06)

Minor drugs: They are less harmful than major natural drugs to humans, both natural and synthetic, and are represented in the following:

- 1) **Coffee and tea (caffeine):** Caffeine is one of the substances that affects the brain, as well as behavior and mood. It has a stimulating and stimulating effect on the brain, and continuing to consume it results in several harms, so scientists have classified caffeine among the substances that cause dependence.
- 2) **Coca:** A tropical tree whose scientific name is *Coca Acuminata*, native to Africa, contains caffeine, oil, and choline glucide, and its seeds are used in beverages and medicine.
- 3) **Nut Al-Tayeb:** Its scientific name is *Meristica Fragrance*, from the seed coat another spice is extracted, and from the seed and its coat is oil used in medicine (Khaled Hamad, 2013, p. 42).

Drug classifications

The term narcotic drugs is classified into several types, either in terms of color, type, or source, and the classifications of narcotic drugs are addressed according to different criteria, and the Algerian legislator also considered the seriousness of this crime and that it is one of the most widespread and diverse criminal phenomena, and allocated a specific penalty for it under

Law 04/18 In order to limit and eliminate the effects of this serious crime, narcotic substances were classified into (Haimer Zoulikha, 2018, p. 8).

First: According to the type of anesthetic

Natural drugs: These are drugs that exist in their natural form, without any chemical changes, and they are of plant origin, the most important of which are hashish and opium, Coca (Hadi Ali Youssef Bouhamza, 2004, p. 16)

Synthetic drugs: The narcotic substance is extracted from the natural plant and other substances are added to it before it is sold in the market, and it has a greater and greater effect than what the drug consumed in its natural form, including morphine and heroin (Haimer Zuleikha, 2018, p. 9)

Synthetic drugs: These are those that are synthesized and manufactured in laboratories based on chemical compounds, and are not extracted from natural drugs, and they have a different effect, some of which are stimulating to the nervous system and some of which have a stimulating effect (Al-Hadi Ali Youssef Bouhamza, 2004, p. 16)

Second: According to its effect on humans

They differ in terms of their effect on mental and psychological activity and are divided into stimulant and analgesic:

Stimulant drugs: These are drugs that have an effect on the nervous system and the psychological state, especially in cases of frustration and depression, the most important of which are cocaine, benzidine, and mescaline.

Analgesic drugs: They lead to stagnation and lethargy because they slow down the mental activity of those who use them. They are divided into opioid analgesic drugs consisting of opium and its derivatives, and non-opioid analgesic drugs that have the same effect as the first type, except that they have no relation to opium, as it is not included in their composition (Iman Muhammad Al-Jabri, 2011, p. 20)

Third: According to its seriousness

It is based on the danger of the narcotic substance and is divided into:

Major drugs: A group of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances that have a significant and dangerous effect on humans, including hashish, opium, heroin, morphine, cocaine, and hallucinogenic drugs.

Minor narcotics: including sleeping drugs, sedative drugs, coca and khat, as well as caffeine, tea and coffee (Fatima Al-Arfi, 2004, p. 38)

History of drugs

The use of narcotic drugs dates back to about 5000 years BC, that is, since ancient times, and thus they are not the product of this era. Rather, man has known them since the first prehistoric times (Al-Zahra Brik, 2009/2010, p. 28.) In many countries, they believe that drugs and their use began recently, but the truth confirms that since the existence of man on the face of the earth, he has been trying to change his mood. In the past, current drugs did not exist, and the ancients used plants found in forests to treat organic disease, and to relieve injuries from wars and battles, and through these plants they discovered that some of them change the mood through experimentation ‘They were able to distinguish between types of narcotic plants, after scientific discoveries and the development of medical and pharmaceutical science, other types

of narcotic drugs were discovered, such as sedative, hypnotic, and stimulant drugs (Raqiq Najma, 2016-2017, p. 51) The use of poppy seeds, hemp, and coca leaves was widespread in many civilizations, such as China, Greece, Romans, and India, and the contemporary beginnings of the use of narcotic drugs were especially in the West for medical purposes and objectives, so opium was known since 7000 years BC as a substance prescribed to treat some diseases such as colic in children and even to treat Insomnia, diarrhea, and nerve inflammation, because they were ignorant of the risks resulting from the effects of taking this substance ‘As for India, opium was known in the sixth century AD, and its use varied between abuse on the one hand and medicine on the other hand (Haimer Zulekha, 2018, p. 2)

The first traces of the use of drugs date back to the Egyptian Pharaonic civilization, while the first writings of addictive effects date back to the Chinese Emperor Shan Ning in the year 2700 BC. Ad (Al-Zahra Brik, 2009/2010, p. 28) As for cannabis, it was used 4000 years before AD in Asia and northwestern China, then it spread throughout the world and reached India 1500 years BC. In Africa, its use began in the eleventh century AD (Haimer Zuleikha, 2018, p. 2) As for khat, its use became famous in the Red Sea region, especially Yemen, around the 14th century AD, and it was taken by chewing it. There was a relationship between the use of narcotic substances, cannabis and coca, and religious rituals, in the belief that the use of narcotic substances facilitates the process of contact with the world of spirits or With unseen powers, its consumption is limited only to a specific social group ‘Coca was reserved for the elite, priests, and ruling hegemony, and it was forbidden to the rest of the people, especially women (Brahmin Nasira 2013, p. 17)

As for Algeria, some studies have indicated that Algerians’ knowledge of drugs dates back to before the French occupation, based on the novel of the late Heisich von Marstan, titled Hashish Smokers in the City of Algiers, and what supports this proposal is the spread of hashish cultivation throughout the Ottoman Empire ‘It was used as a sweat, and after the advent of French colonialism, what is known as absinthe was introduced, which causes severe intoxication, especially if it is not mixed with water (Brahmiyya Nasira 2013, p. 18)

Also, hashish was not legally prohibited at that time, as Algerians used it in cafes, and after independence, Algeria was considered one of the countries suffering from the phenomenon of drugs that cast a shadow on Algerian society, and the first warning was recorded in 1975 after 3 tons of Cannabis (Brahmiyya Nasira 2013, p. 19)

As for the Islamic world, drugs were not known during the era of the Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, but they spread after him due to the Islamic conquests and the Persians entered Islamic countries, and with the passage of time the Arab countries became a market for these materials and their various types.

When doctors in general and the general public realized the dangers of drugs that had spread widely beginning in the 19th century, it became impossible to determine their use in a specific region of the world, and in the 20th century, it became clear that the problems emanating from drugs required measures aimed at preventing smuggling from One country to another, otherwise it would appear with the expansion of trade and communications (Al-Zahra Break, 2009/2010, p. 29)

Causes of drug abuse

The problem of drug abuse does not have one side, as it is considered one of the pathological social phenomena in the world, especially in civilized areas, so the problem of

drug abuse is not one-sided, but rather there are influential factors that result in resorting to drug abuse, and among these factors are:

- Obtaining pleasure, as it is known, is imaginary and temporary.
- Inappropriate family social conditions, family disintegration or delinquency of one of the parents.
- Escape with some of life's pressures and hospitals.
- Parents' rejection of the child or teenager, the father's evasion of responsibility, and the lack of parents' ambitions regarding their children's future.
- Decrease in the individual's religious motivation and the failure of the family, school, and society to highlight religious orders and prohibitions.
- Bad treatment in some media outlets (Khaled Hamad Al-Muhannadi, 2013, pp. 63, 64)

These reasons are due to:

1) The individual pushes himself to take drugs because of:

- Weak religious motivation of the individual abuser: Young people's failure to fully adhere to the teachings of the true Islamic religion by following its commands and avoiding its prohibitions.
- Sitting or accompanying bad companions: This is through the factor of curiosity and the insistence of friends, the most important incentive for experimentation as a method of one-on-one participation with these friends.
- Belief in increased sexual ability: Young people believe there is a close relationship between drug use and increased sexual ability in terms of achieving maximum sexual satisfaction and prolonging intercourse for married couples (Raqiq Najma, 2016-2017, p. 159)
- Traveling abroad: This is due to the presence of all means of temptation and places of entertainment and the lack of control over the places where drugs are taken.
- Feeling empty: The presence of emptiness with the lack of suitable places that absorb the energy of youth, such as clubs and parks, and it is considered one of the reasons that lead to the abuse of intoxicants and drugs.
- Love of imitation: Some teenagers' attempt to prove themselves and their premature masculinity by imitating adults in their actions, especially those related to smoking or abuse, in order to give them a masculine character (Raqiq Najma, 2016-2017, p. 161)
- Staying up late outside the home: It is considered absolute freedom, and some people stay up late outside the home in places that encourage drunkenness and drugs.
- Availability of money in abundance: In the hands of some young people, it pushes them to buy the most expensive food and drink, and curiosity and bad companions may push them to buy the most expensive drugs (Khaled Hamad Al-Muhannadi, 2013, p. 68)

2) The family pushes the individual to take drugs because of:

- Bad role models by parents: One of the most important factors that push young people to abuse is when parents appear in front of their children in a shameful way, represented by them engaging in bad behavior while they are under the drug.
- Addiction of a parent: This addiction directly affects family ties as a result of the constant disagreements it entails, which pushes children to deviate.
- Parents' preoccupation with their children: This is due to their preoccupation with work and travel and not following up and monitoring them, which makes the children more vulnerable to loss and falling into the abyss of addiction.
- Inequality between spouses: In this case, the children are seriously affected by this, so both parties are keen to remind the other of his financial condition, which causes disagreements and as a result the house turns into hell, and both parties or one of them flees for the sake of comfort, and in this case the children are lost and Their result is deviance (Raqiq Najma, 2016-2017, p. 164)
- Excessive cruelty to children: By treating parents harshly (severe beatings and reprimands), his behavior is reversed, leading to disobedience to parents, leaving home, running away, and resorting to a society of evil people.
- Family pressure on the son to excel: This is in order to demand that the children excel in their studies, even though it is not possible to achieve this. They may resort to using some stimulant and stimulant drugs in order to stay up late, study, and learn lessons. (Raqiq Najma, 2016-2017, p. 164)

3) Society pushes the individual to use drugs because of:

- Availability of addictive substances through smugglers and promoters: one of the most important factors that belong to society and that makes drug use easy for young people, and this is due to each society containing misguided, corrupt individuals and trying to corrupt them for other members of society.
- The existence of some entertainment places in some societies: There are some entertainment places that rely mainly on the presence of narcotic and intoxicating substances in order to extort the money of their patrons, and their owners only care about collecting money.
- Economic openness: Some weak-minded people attempt to exploit the economy badly instead of importing necessary goods for members of society, so they trade and smuggle drugs illegally (Khaled Hamad Al-Muhannadi, 2013, pp. 72,73)

Theories explaining drug abuse

1) Biological theory

Genetic explanation: This trend explains the phenomenon of addiction as a hereditary process such that drug complications increase the families of addicts in particular, as the results of studies conducted on twins resulted in the fact that the two brothers are more similar in their habits of taking drugs than the two non-twin brothers, and the results of studies that focused on Adoption: Children born to parents who are not addicted to drugs ·However, children born to parents addicted to drugs did not show an increase in addiction rates, while children born to

parents addicted to drugs and adopted by non-addicted parents have four to five times higher rates of drug addiction than children born non-addicted to drugs.

Physiological explanation:

The interests of this trend are mainly attributed to the chemical structure of the anesthetic in terms of its effects on the body. On the one hand, this trend is concerned with explaining how dependence on a drug occurs, and in this regard, there are substances that the brain naturally secretes to relieve our pain. This trend also explains addiction on the basis of the presence of two types of receptors on the membrane of the nerve cell wall, drug receptors whose interaction with the drug leads to its drug effect, and static and inactive receptors that do not interact with the drug. Continuous drug use leads to the activation of static receptors to transform into drug receptors, which leads to The individual's condition leads to increased doses.

2) Freud's theory (psychoanalysis)

It provided an explanation for addictive behavior and shed light on one aspect of the problem, as support for drug use is an important motivation for repeated use, as well as the fear of painful withdrawal symptoms, and failure and feelings of frustration and tension are among the motivations for use, as well as emptiness and a state of loss. This theory considers that without neglecting the chemical properties of the drug and its effects, the problem of addiction does not lie in the drug, but in the person who uses it.

And the level of maturity that he has reached, because this level is what determines the methods of his compatibility with life. This school also believes that the individual who turns to abuse has a tendency to do so before he realizes the numbing effects, so when he resorts to it, he seeks security and reassurance, and it also believes that the user satisfies His internal psychological needs (Basma Movements, 2013, pp. 62-63)

3) Cognitive theory

The problem of addiction exists in a group of ideas that descend from the basic idea of self-loathing, as this idea combines with the stress of daily life to produce depression and aggression, and these situations activate related thoughts with the feeling of need that will be associated with drugs.

4) Behavioral theory

You see that drug addiction or getting used to it is a type of habit that has become part of the addict's lifestyle, and it is difficult to get rid of it. This habit has become entrenched under the influence of euphoria and positive feelings, as there are drugs that create physiological dependence and cause symptoms of withdrawal in the event of interruption and fear of withdrawal symptoms and His pain (Basma Movements, 2013, p. 64)

Means of combating and treating drug abuse.

Before delving into how to contain drug addicts and help them return to what is right and readapt them in their societies and make them active people in society, transforming from a destructive element into a creative and effective one, it is worth examining the essence of the problem before it occurs and how to avoid any of taking incorrect methods

This is done through what is called prevention to avoid the danger and avoid it before the disease becomes severe and difficult to treat, from which the levels and forms of prevention can be determined **as follows:**

Primary prevention: It seeks, through education, media, and propaganda, to prevent the emergence of diseases, non-preventive behaviors, or social ills such as drugs.

Second prevention: It seeks through early diagnosis and treatment of disorders and behaviors while preventing the spread and exacerbation of these diseases in society.

Third prevention: Here, the disease or disorders have appeared through this type of prevention, and those working in this field try to identify and limit the dangers of these diseases and pests by developing effective types of treatment so that they can be dealt with and eliminated (Buhara Hanaa, 2017, p. 287)

Treatment methods varied through:

1) Psychiatric: This is done through a team of nurses, which undertakes to examine the patient and prescribe treatment in the form of medications, within the framework of a treatment process represented by the following medications:

- Metadone: Taking it on a daily basis does not provide euphoria or peak anesthetic effect.
- Cyptex: A replacement substance given by general doctors.
- Nozinan - Largactil: Sedative medications, the amounts of which are given according to the addict's condition.
- Laroxil, Anafranil: anti-degeneration medications and prevention of this condition that precedes cessation of use.
- Tebgretil: Anti-mood medications used to prevent neuropsychiatric phenomena associated with menopause.
- Painkillers and antispasmodics in case of pain.
- Treatment with B1. b2 vitamins: alcohol analgesics.

The post-treatment stage is considered the most difficult in the patient care process (Sindra Muwaffaq, 2008, p. 165)

2) Psychological care: It consists of individual or group psychological and therapeutic assistance, as well as support from the environment and family therapy, carried out by specialists in clinical psychology, there are two prevailing trends according to which different therapeutic approaches are conducted.

3) Cognitive-behavioral current: It depends on direct treatment of the symptoms that appear in the patient in order to reduce their severity, and this treatment focuses on developing behavior strategies aimed at changing the patient's relationship with those who pose problems to him.

4) Psychoanalytic stream: This treatment is given to what the patient tells from his family and personal history and appears through his words, crises, and involuntary desires in order to draw inspiration from treatment from these signs.

5) Social educational care: It depends on listening, support, and guidance in treatment centers, and in this type of treatment, patients are suggested to perform many activities,

recreational operations, and ergonomic therapy, and thus sociology transforms the patient's work and removes him from his negativity and Breaking his isolation imposed on him by drugs (Al-Zahra Brik, 2009, pp. 48-49)

THE CONCLUSION

From what we have discussed in these lectures, we conclude that addiction to drugs is one of the most prominent and widespread disorders that individuals and societies suffer from, as it does not only affect the individual abuser, but goes beyond him to affect the stability of the family and even the structure of society, as well as its safety and stability 'This is due to the negative social effects that accompany it, such as theft, divorce, disintegration, and other reasons that make young people resort to using drugs, which results in deviations and crimes, making the person who uses drugs a social outcast, a family abomination, and a security pursuer, all of these characteristics that have stuck to him out of his desire or Against his will, it causes him to live in a state of schizophrenia and dissatisfaction with himself, which leads to destabilization. The addict lives in a state of confusion between what he refuses to reform on his own and between family and societal ostracism, the latter of which hinders his attempt to recover, and this addict needs family embrace and welcome from his community, receiving him with all its institutions and bodies to combat this phenomenon.

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